

A STUDY ON FAILURE BEHAVIOR OF HYBRID COMPOSITES
UNDER STATIC AND FATIGUE TORSIONAL LOADINGS

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ABSTRACT

The experimental tests, under shear loading, of the glass fiber composites, the carbon fiber composites and the carbon/glass hybrid composites are carried out. The "Hybrid Effect" in shear stress state has been found. The non-linear stress-strain relation of composites caused by the material damage and the shear behavior of the matrix is discussed. The stiffness retention coefficient after lamina failure is proposed. The failure process of hybrid laminates is analyzed by HCAP (Hybrid Composites Analysis Program) which was developed by using the incremental method. The shear stress-strain relation by the numerical calculation is compared with the experimental results of hybrid laminates. The contrastive experiments between glass composites and hybrid composites are performed on MTS test machine under fatigue torsional loadings. And the life of the hybrid composites is about twice of that for the glass composites with the same shear strain amplitudes. The failure mechanism of the hybrid composites under both static and fatigue shear loadings is also studied.

KEYWORDS: Hybrid; Loading, shear; Nonlinear; Failure mechanism

1. INTRODUCTION

The hybrid composites has been widely used in many applications since 1970's for its excellent properties. The mechanical behavior of hybrid composites and so-called "Hybrid Effect" have been studied in many references, where the investigation under simple axial stress state is much more than under other stress states. For example, there are few papers about them under torsional loading. Specially, the study on behavior of hybrid composites under fatigue torsional moments is seldom reported in literature.

So, we make an effort to investigate some mechanical properties of the hybrid

composites under static and fatigue torque loadings. The major work of this paper is listed as follows:

- (1) The "Hybrid Effect" of hybrid composites under torsional condition is studied.
- (2) The main factors causing non-linear behavior of hybrid composites are discussed. The stiffness retention coefficient after the lamina failure is determined. By using the incremental method, a program, Hybrid Composites Analysis Program (HCAP), is developed to analyze non-linear failure process in the case of plane stress.
- (3) The comparative tests of pure glass, carbon fiber composites and hybrid composites subjected to static and cyclic torsional loadings are carried out, and the failure mechanism are investigated.

As a part of development of hybrid composites driveshaft tube, the specimens used in the paper are composed of three types of composite laminates: [G \pm 45], [C0/90] and [G \pm 45, C0/90, G \pm 45], among which the third has been determined as the fundamental laminates structure of the driveshaft tube based on a large number of calculations and experimental tests [1]. By the way, we selected neither pure glass nor pure carbon fiber composites, because the former does not satisfy the axial rigidity requirement and the later is too dear. But the hybrid composites driveshaft tube can satisfy both mechanical and economical needs.

2. "HYBRID EFFECT" OF HYBRID COMPOSITES UNDER TORSIONAL LOADING

Hybrid composites with two kinds of fiber has both fibers characteristics and "Hybrid Effect" which behavior is superior to original one after hybridized. Hayashi [2] found out "Hybrid Effect" of the hybrid composites under tensile loading, i.e. the crack strain of hybrid composites is larger than that of the composites with either low elongation fiber. Is it sure under torsional loading?

We discuss the specimens as mentioned above, of which the property parameters are shown in Table 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

Table 1. Elastic modulus of constituents

	E_L (GPa)	V_{LT}	G_{LT} (GPa)
Carbon fiber	196.3	0.32	39.21
Glass fiber	68.6	0.31	28.13
Epoxy resin	3.53	0.36	1.36

Table 2. Structures of specimens

Specimens	Fibers and angle(deg)	Thickness(t_i)
I	[G \pm 45]	G+45: 0.5, G-45: 0.5
II	[C0/90]	C0: 0.5, C90: 0.5
III	[G \pm 45,C0/90,G \pm 45]	G \pm 45:0.286, C0/90:0.428, G \pm 45:0.286

Table 3. Elastic Modulus of Laminae

	E_L (GPa)	E_T (GPa)	ν_{LT}	G_{LT} (GPa)
Glass	37.3	9.62	0.28	3.66
Carbon	102.4	9.92	0.33	4.35

Figure 1(a) illustrates a stress element from the torsional pipe. The glass directions of the winding are at $\pm 45^\circ$ angles, which are the same as principal stresses under pure shear stress. In this case, the deformation is described as Figure 1(b).

Figure 1. Stress and strain elements from torsional pipe

We obtain from Figure 1(b):

$$\operatorname{tg}(45^\circ + \epsilon_{XY}) = (1 + \epsilon_T) / (1 - \epsilon_L)$$

$$\epsilon_{XY} = \epsilon_L + \epsilon_T$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_L &= \sigma_L / E_L - \nu_{LT} * \sigma_T / E_T \\ &= \tau_{xy} (1/E_L + \nu_{LT}/E_T) \\ \epsilon_T &= \tau_{xy} (1/E_T + \nu_{TL}/E_L)\end{aligned}$$

The shear stress and the shear strain are related within linear range as follows:

$$G_{xy} = \tau_{xy} / \epsilon_{xy} \quad (1)$$

So, the shear modulus of the laminates is:

$$(Gc)_{xy} = E_L / (1 + E_L/E_T + 2\nu_{TL}) \quad (2)$$

For $E_L = 37.3 \text{ GPa}$, $E_T = 9.62 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{LT} = 0.28$

$$(Gc)_{xy} = 7.43 \text{ GPa}$$

The shear modulus for laminates of carbon layers winding angles of 0° and 90° can be calculated by using the laminate plate theory:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ A_{61} & A_{62} & A_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \epsilon_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) can be rewritten:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \epsilon_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ B_{61} & B_{62} & B_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where $[A_{ij}]$ is stiffness matrix, in which the components are:

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{m=1}^n (Q_{ij})_m t_m \quad (5)$$

and $[B_{ij}]$ is compliance matrix.

Normal stress σ_x and σ_y are zero now. The relation of shear stress, τ_{xy} , and shear strain, ϵ_{xy} , is simply written from Equation (4)

$$\epsilon_{xy} = B_{66} \tau_{xy} \quad (6)$$

Making a comparison between Equation (1) and (6), we can obtain:

$$(Gc)_{xy} = 1/B_{66}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}B_{66} &= (A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2) / D \\ D &= \begin{vmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ A_{61} & A_{62} & A_{66} \end{vmatrix}\end{aligned}$$

The components A_{ij} are replaced with the numerical datas, which are obtained by calculating a series of equations as listed above. We have:

$$(Gc)_{xy} = 4.35 \text{ GPa}$$

Obviously, Specimen I is a material with "high modulus" under our condition. The higher modulus, the smaller crack strain is in a general case, which are presented by the tests (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. "Hybrid Effect" of Hybrid Composites under Torsion
 I. Shear stress-strain curve of [G±45].
 II. Shear stress-strain curve of [C0/90].
 III. Shear stress-strain curve of [G±45,C0/90,G±45]

Curve I or Curve II indicates the relation between shear stress and strain of [G±45] or [C0/90]. From the test curve, Curve III, of hybrid composites, we can observe the strain at the point A is equal to failure strain of [G±45], and the failure strain at the point A' now is larger than that at the point A. Particularly, we arrive at a result as follows:

$$(\epsilon_{xyA'} - \epsilon_{xyA}) / \epsilon_{xyA} * 100\% = 25.5\%$$

Torsional "Hybrid Effect" similar to tensile has been proved. This effect is utilizable in resistance of impact.

3. NON-LINEAR BEHAVIOR AND FAILURE MECHANISM OF HYBRID COMPOSITES

The Non-linear behavior of hybrid composites is mainly caused by two factors which are the stiffness degradation of the failure lamina and the non-linear shear behavior of the matrix.

The shear stress-strain relation of composites is clearly non-linear, which has been proved by many experiments.

The classical failure criterions assume that a failure lamina is not able to subject to any loads, and the corresponding rigidity vanishes after failure. As pointed out by Reference [3], [4]: a ply in a laminates does not satisfy Failure Criterion, then, it still has certain loading capability or residual stiffness. By analysing the results of experiments and numerical calculations [5], [6], the stiffness degradation after ply-failure is a gradual procedure

showing obvious non-linear behavior.

Further study shows that the stiffness of the failure lamina will be retained within a range. According to numerical calculations, coefficient of stiffness retention is suggested from 0.6 to 0.9 for a compressive damaged lamina.

So, it is necessary to consider non-linear effects in calculating the stress and strain of the laminates. In order to analyze the laminates with non-linear behavior, linear elastic relation is assumed between the small increments of stress and strain. Thus, the equations are similar to laminated plate theory after the stress and strain are respectively replaced by the increments of stress and strain. They are familiar to all and are not listed here. Only is a calculating result given in Figure 3 (flow diagram of HCAP program and the detailed analysis are discussed in Reference [6]).

Figure 3. Experimental and Theoretical Curves of Shear Stress-strain of Hybrid Composites
 (a). Solid Line: Experimental curve.
 (b). Dotted Line: Theoretical curve.

For compressive stiffness retention coefficient after lamina failure is equal to 0.8, we obtain the predicted theoretical Curve B, which agrees reasonably well with experimental Curve A of hybrid composites.

As motioned above, the directions of glass fibers of $[G\pm 45]$ and $[G\pm 45, C0/90, G\pm 45]$ are the same as the principal stress under sheara loading. Both failures are caused by the micro-buckling of the 45° fibers, which subject to the principal compressive stress (see Figure 4 and 5). The crack directions in the graphs are perpendicular to the principal compressive stress.

Figure 4. Failure of glass laminates under torque loading.

Figure 5. Failure of hybrid laminates under torque loading.

4. FATIGUE FAILURE BEHAVIOR OF HYBRID COMPOSITES

After having satisfied the static mechanical requirement, it is necessary for driveshaft tube to have good fatigue resistance. In this section, the fatigue behaviors of glass composites and hybrid composites are presented using the form of the ratio of shear modulus and the number of cycles (G/G_0-N).

In addition, some mechanism of fatigue failures are also discussed.

The contrastive tests of glass composites and hybrid composites are carried out. The tests are composed of group I and II. Here, the loads are symmetrical cycle in Group I and pulsating cycle in Group II, respectively.

Table 4.

	A: [G±45]	B: [G±45, C0/90, G±45]
I	symmetry	pulsation
II	symmetry	pulsation

In order to compare, all of the maximum stresses, τ_{max} , correspond to the same shear strain ϵ_{xy} , for $\epsilon_{xy}=1.11\%$,

$$(\tau_c)_{max}=80\text{MPa}, (\tau_{Hy})_{max}=64\text{MPa},$$

which are determined by Curve I and III in Figure 2.

Fatigue damage often results in a significant reduction of modulus of the composite laminates. Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the change of shear modulus under loadings as listed in Table 4.

Figure 6. Changes in modulus under symmetrical torsional loadings.

Figure 7. Changes in modulus under pulsating torsional loadings.

The experimental curves indicate hardly any stiffness change of composites until immediately before failure, and the fatigue life of hybrid composite pipes are about twice of that for the glass composite pipes with the same shear strain amplitudes, whether symmetrical or pulsating cyclic loadings.

Figure 8. failure of $[G\pm 45, C0/90, G\pm 45]$ under fatigue torsional loading.

The experimental results exhibit very complex failure mechanisms under static and fatigue loadings. In the same way, failures of laminates are yielded by kinking of those fibers bearing compressive stress (see Figure 8).

5. CONCLUSIONS

- (1). The "Hybrid Effect" of hybrid composites under shear loading is proved by the numerical calculation and the experimental tests, i.e. the deformation property of the composites with smaller crack strain can be improved after hybridized.
- (2). The non-linear behavior should be considered when calculating laminate strength. The stiffness retention coefficient after lamina failures has been suggested from 0.6 to 0.9.
- (3). For the composites with fiber in the 45° directions under shear loading, it is concluded that the micro-buckling of the 45° fibers will cause static and fatigue failures.
- (4). The fatigue life of hybrid composites is about twice of that for the glass composites with the same shear strain amplitudes.

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